
Comparative Study on Perception of Urban vs Rural Organic Jaggery Consumers of Satara Taluka

Ms. Pai Vandana Narasimha

Research Scholar, D. G. College of Commerce, Satara.

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15147063

Abstract:

Food is one of the essential needs of human beings (as of all creatures) and agriculture is the prime source of food of all living beings. Man has been responsible for the origin of agriculture very early in his evolution. Human beings continued to practice, evolve and develop this science of producing food in its manifold aspects in all ages and regions of the world. Twentieth century has been the witness of most technological agricultural changes leaving remarks on rural landscape and population. This technical revolution, which is continuing to be dominant method for food production, depends on on-farm and off farm resource usage. Invention of machinery has put labour out of farm while variety of chemical fertilizers have increased yield without any concern of environmental measures for economic reasons. Sustainable food production became more and more vital after facing with social, ecological and economic impacts of industrialized agriculture. Societies find solution by demanding for low-input, regional and seasonal products with the respect of environment, health and social welfare of the region. There have been organizations and policies have been established in developed countries to take measures in food production.

Keyword: Perception, Organic Jaggery, Jaggery Consumer etc.

Introduction:

Food is one of the essential needs of human beings (as of all creatures) and agriculture is the prime source of food of all living beings. Man has been responsible for the origin of agriculture very early in his evolution. Human beings continued to practice, evolve and develop this science of producing food in its manifold aspects in all ages and regions of the world. Twentieth century has been the witness of most technological agricultural changes leaving remarks on rural landscape and population. This technical revolution, which is continuing to be dominant method for food production, depends on on-farm and off farm resource usage. Invention of machinery has put labour out of farm while variety of chemical fertilizers have increased yield without any concern of environmental measures for economic reasons. Sustainable

food production became more and more vital after facing with social, ecological and economic impacts of industrialized agriculture. Societies find solution by demanding for low-input, regional and seasonal products with the respect of environment, health and social welfare of the region. There have been organizations and policies have been established in developed countries to take measures in food production. Organic Agriculture as one solution to problems of industrialized agriculture based on Holistic Production Management systems which aims creating integrated, humane, environmentally and economically sustainable agricultural production systems. Consumers of industrialized countries have shown a great attention towards organic products starting from 90.s. Food safety and quality issues have triggered the awareness of consumers

and people start to be suspicious towards conventional products. Moreover, today's educated society is showing great interest to their and children's health and prefer foods with more nutritional values, less additives and more coming from natural production methods. Consumers increased knowledge about the relationship between diet and health, and their awareness of food quality features, as well as their access to information about new production and processing technologies have resulted in a constantly increasing demand for improved quality food; being organic food within this trend. Food consumption patterns are rapidly changing nowadays as a result of environmental issues, concern about the nutritional value of food and health issues. Organic farming is a technique, which involves cultivation of plants and rearing of animals in natural ways. This process involves the use of biological materials, avoiding synthetic substances to maintain soil fertility and ecological balance thereby minimizing pollution and wastage. It relies on ecologically balanced agricultural principles like crop rotation, green manure, organic waste, biological pest control, mineral and rock additives. While Consumer perception is a marketing concept that encompasses a customer's impression, awareness and or consciousness about a company or its offerings. It is typically affected by advertising, reviews, public relations, social media, personal experience and other channels.

Review of Literature:

Brijesh Sivathanu (2015) have identified the factors affecting consumers' preference towards organic food products. The main aim of the study was to understand the preference of consumers and to identify the factors influencing consumers towards organic food products. Both primary and secondary data were used. The primary data were collected with structured questionnaire and five point likert scaling technique. An

exploratory study was conducted after an extensive literature survey. The sample size was used to find out the determinants of preference among the consumers. The results indicate that the reasons for consumers preference to buy organic food products are various factors including demographic characteristics of the consumers. It has been observed that the females have more preference for organic foods as compared to male consumers and also more number of respondents is educated people between the age group of 29-39 years. People who have higher income prefer organic foods and their perception of organic food is healthy, safe, high nutritional value and environment friendly products. The research brought out some suggestions that the determinants of consumers preference towards organic food products and which will be useful to the marketers to design a suitable marketing mix and to incorporate and implement the various marketing strategies by the marketers and other factors impacting the preference of the consumers in the various strategies of the society. Also there is a need to build up more trust among the consumers and get the proper government certification for the organic food products.

S. Amutha and M. Kanagarathinam (2017) have released a study on "Consumers' Preference for OFP." 550 customers made up the sample size, and a convenient sampling technique was applied. The Friedman rank test and chi-square were used to gather and examine the data. According to the study's findings, the majority of consumers are married, retired workers who have a strong preference for organic foods. Organic food products are highly preferred by the majority of consumers who read food labels before making an organic purchase. The Friedman test results show that the majority of consumers choose to purchase organic food goods for three primary reasons: price, freshness, and increased income.

Dasari. Pandurangarao, K.Chiranjeevi, D. Suryachandra Rao(2017)have discovered the elements influencing Hyderabad and Secuderabad consumers' decisions to purchase OFP. 500 customers made up the study's sample, and they were questioned using a standardized questionnaire to look at the main determining elements to make use of organic food items. Factor analysis, reliability testing, and percentage analysis were used to examine the data. The results of a factor analysis test of 35 variables showed that 10 factors—labels, health and environmental concerns, brand, advertising, safety, accessibility, price, freshness, and store location—were the most important. The three main issues that influenced the decision to purchase OFP were safety, the environment, and health. They recommended that the marketers create environmental and health-related advertising initiatives. Thus, the organic sector is still in its early stages. extensive marketing push to raise awareness of OFPs and Urban and semi-urban consumption can support the growth of organic food markets.

R.Ayaswarya and S.Vasanthi (2018)have tried to gauge Thirucirappalli Corporation's "Consumer level of preference towards organic food products." 50 responders were chosen as the research sample utilizing stratified random sampling methods, and one-way ANOVA and percentage analysis were used to examine the data that was gathered. They stated that the study's importance lay in raising consumer awareness and influencing their tastes and inclinations, which will raise demand for organic products both domestically and internationally. Because they are chemical-free, environmentally friendly, and address health issues, people favor organic products over conventional ones. The alternative hypothesis was accepted in the analysis, while the null hypothesis was rejected. The researchers ultimately come to the conclusion that consumers' concerns about the environment and their health have led to

an increase in their preferences. An additional OFP preference was the OFP's taste and natural appearance.

Research Gap:

The researcher has made extensive spade work and collected research studies and literature reviews pertaining to the objectives. After studying the collected literature and research papers, it is found that many of the studies concentrated on consumer buying behavior, consumer perception, awareness level, buying intention, factors influencing towards purchasing of organic food products. But no comparative study location-based is done in specific organic product .

Statement of Problem:

In emerging nations, use of pesticides in agriculture is becoming a significant health hazard. Since the Pandemic of Covid-19, favouritism for organic food has risen significantly and it is seen in customers and vendors reactions through alteration of food habits. On the other side can the reason behind such alteration can be like wellness and environmental issues or other reason like vendors, doctor's reference. The researcher was having following questions into her mind before conducting the present study: Do the urban and rural consumers' have same perception while purchasing organic jaggery? What is the reason behind purchase of organic jaggery?

Does anything motivate consumers towards organic jaggery consumption?

Objectives of the Study:

The current intends to combine the themes extracted from recent works of literature, which serve as a base for more exhaustive research, as well as the data collected from the present scenario to determine area-wise consumer buying patterns towards organic jaggery. In precise, the research fundamentally aims to inspect

the significant attributes influencing the consumer's purchase decision-making structure. A holistic view of interrelation among the variables which affect rural and urban consumer's purchase intent concerning organic jaggery of Satara Taluka.

The research objectives proposed are:

To investigate the factors influencing consumer perception of rural and urban consumers towards organic jaggery in Satara Taluka.

To study the effect of selected demographic factors on consumer's perception towards organic jaggery choice of rural and urban consumers in Satara Taluka.

Hypothesis:

H₀: There is a significant relationship between location of the residence of consumers' and their perception in purchase of organic jaggery.

H₁: There is a no significant relationship between location of the residence of consumers' and their perception in purchase of organic jaggery.

Scope:

The study, which was carried out in satara city and five villages of Satara Taluka,

aims to determine perception that organic jaggery consumer has which ultimately resulted in his/her purchase.

Limitations of the study:

The present research is limited to the following:

The study was conducted among the organic jaggery consumers of Satara City and 5 villages of Satara Taluka only The sample size was limited to 50 respondents from both categories.

The primary source of collection was used which will may be not embrace the same findings for whole district, state or country.

Research Methodology:

The primary and secondary data were used for data collection. The secondary data were collected from various websites, journals and magazines. The primary data was collected by means of structured interview schedule. Convenient sampling techniques has been used in the study and the sample size is 50 , In order to analyse the objectives of the study, several statistical methods are tested.

Analysis and Interpretation:

1. Frequency table on Demographic:

Profile of Respondents:

Demographic Profile	Frequency	Percentage	
Age	Below 20	7	15
	21-40	13	25
	41-60	25	50
	Above 60	5	10
Gender	Male	24	47
	Female	26	53
Marital Status	Married	29	58
	Unmarried	21	42
Total Family Members	1-3	19	39
	4-6	21	41
	7 and above	10	20
Educational Qualification	SSC	4	9
	HSC	15	30

	Diploma	5	10
	Graduate	26	51
Occupational Status	Government Service	13	26
	Private Service	10	20
	Business	10	20
	Farming	15	30
	Retired	2	4
Monthly Income (in Rupees)	Below 10000	2	4
	10001-20000	35	70
	20001-30000	8	16
	Above 30000	5	10
Location	Urban	25	50
	Rural	25	50
Total Respondents		50	100

Altogether the responses from fifty participants were taken into consideration. Based on the above (Table 1.9.1), age was taken as the number of years completed by the respondent at the time of study conducted, and respondents were classified into four groups based on their age as there were four classes of age from Below 20, 21-40, from 41-60, and Above 60 . Most participants fall in the age group between 41-60 years old, making 50% of the participants, which indicates that a large number of middle-aged people are well aware of organic products and tend to purchase more organic jaggery when compared to the young and old-aged group. Participants were identified as either male or female. Results reveal that ,Females are more willing to participate and tend to showcase an increased likeliness towards purchasing organic jaggery. Considering the respondent's marital status, they were identified as either married or unmarried.

Out of the total respondents, married people are more eager to purchase organic jaggery. Concerning the total number of people in the family, most of the people who actively participated and purchased organic products belong to a family consisting of 4-6 members. Most of the respondents purchasing organic jaggery had graduation, Therefore it is inferred that people who are qualified tend to show increased purchase behaviour. Regarding occupational status, most of the participants surveyed were business people, as they were inclined to make organic purchases This outcome shows that individuals with considerable as well as medium income desire to purchase organic products. However, then these respondents are exceptionally influenced by the changes in the price. A slight disparity in the cost of organic produce can influence their purchase pattern. In all 50 respondents were distributes as 25 from rural area and 25 from urban area.

2. Factor's hindering consumer's organic purchase:

Hindering factors	Urban		Rural	
	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank
High Price	9.58		9.18	
Non-availability	9.26		8.45	
Lack of variety	8.21		8.28	
Inability to distinguish	8.06		7.96	
Lack of Trust	7.96		7.56	
Lack of Information	7.12		7.22	

Based on the research, the list mentioned above (Table 1.10.2) displays the factors hindering consumers' organic purchases. As results reveal, most respondents ranked the high cost of organic products as the major contributing factor for non-purchase, with the highest mean of urban was 9.58 while rural was 9.18. Consumers opined that organic products are priced a way higher when compared to conventional products, and hence they could not afford to purchase it on a regular basis even though they are well aware about the health benefits gained out of it. Moreover, unavailability or timely inaccessibility of the needed products were ranked second with a mean of urban was 9.26 while rural was 8.45 and lack of variety in the organic products available in stores were ranked third with a mean score of urban was 8.21 and rural was 8.28, making them go for the conventional ones. Even though we cannot store these items for an extended period since it does not comprise additives and synthetic substances to keep from the bugs, this factor has contributed a lot to the non-purchase of organic products. Most respondents, with a mean score of urban was 8.06 and rural was 7.96, find it challenging to distinguish organic products from other inorganic products. Besides, the lack of trust with urban was 7.96 and rural was 7.56 and a lack of information with a mean score of urban was 7.12 and rural was 7.22 makes their organic purchase difficult. They seem to be unaware of the various certifications and labelling which claims a product as organic. In addition, respondents frequently question the products they get in stores as organic will be organic or not. Lack of information concerning the production technique adopted hinders their organic purchase. It is vital to figure out the causes which restrict or discontinues consumers from organic purchase; thereby, the corrective measure can be adopted by the marketers to improve their purchase

preference. Various articles ought to be delivered to cater to the purchaser's necessities, and the product has to be reasonably priced. Researchers should focus on organic storage procedures without additives.

3. Factor's Motivating Consumer's Organic Purchase:

The list mentioned above (Table 1.10.3) displays the factors which motivate the consumers for repeated organic purchases. The results reveal that product quality was ranked one and considered to be the highest motivating factor, with a mean value of Urban respondents was 9.26 and rural was 9.18. A more significant part of the respondents believed that organic products evade additives and artificial flavouring with no compromise on quality aspects like freshness and nutritional aspects containing lots of vitamins and minerals. Moreover, product quality was guaranteed by the presence of a certified organic logo on the food label and hence proved to be produced with high-quality standards. Benefits gained from consumption were ranked as second with a mean value of Urban respondents was 8.67 and rural was 9.01 as they believed organic consumption enables them to improve their immunity power and is suitable for their skin, teeth, hair, and nails. Apart from the nutritional value, respondents who purchased organic products tend to believe organic products taste better with good appearance than the non-organic products and ranked third with a mean score of urban respondents was 8.24 and rural 8.60. Moreover, they were much attracted to the packaging provided by the organic stores, with a mean score of urban respondents was 8.03 while rural was 8.05. The overall satisfaction attained over the services provided, e.g. parking facility available, home delivery, after-sale services, and timely availability of products in stores, was ranked with a mean score of urban respondents was 6.04 while rural was 6.15.

Finally, the recommendation from friends tends to be the least motivating factor, with a score of urban respondents was 4.11 and rural was 4.25, as respondents always believed in the satisfaction attained through first-hand information or direct experience.

Findings, Suggestion and Conclusion:

Findings:

Hypothesis examined there is no significant relationship between location of the residence of consumers' and their perception in purchase of organic jaggery, and it has been accepted.

Age and purchase intention, majority of regular, occasional and potential buyers of organic jaggery in Satara Taluka fall under the age group of 41-60. It is inferred that youngsters show an increased willingness to purchase organic products since they cannot afford to purchase it on a regular basis; the mid-age group has therefore replaced it with increased financial stability.

Gender and purchase intention, the majority of women in Satara Taluka tend to purchase more frequently when compared to men; they play a prominent role in household decision-making, especially for food items in both urban and rural areas.

Total family members and purchase intentions, majority of the respondents, who are married and have children at home, tend to purchase more of organic jaggery in both urban and rural areas.

Highly educated consumers have more intention to purchase organic jaggery than others in both urban and rural areas. .

Occupational status and income level on purchase intention, farmers are more interested in consumption of organic jaggery in both urban and rural areas.

In both urban and rural areas, Consumers' income level is directly associated with their purchase pattern as the price of organic products are way higher when compared to conventionally grown. Compared to low-income people, medium

and high-income people show a higher likelihood of organic consumption; however, the overall relationship between income and consumption is insignificant.

Word of mouth has strong influence on purchase.

Suggestions:

Despite of the location, Higher percentage of consumers are willing to pay up to a quarter more for organic food than non-organic food. This can be helpful in developing pricing options, especially for organic food marketers.

Location doesn't matter, Although they have several health benefits, organic food has a higher manufacturing cost owing to slower crop development, demanding farming in terms of labour, and a low number of government-induced subsidies. Due to these reasons, there is a challenge in lowering the cost of organic products.

Furthermore, educational programs aimed at improving diet awareness while minimizing diseases might benefit consumers by educating them about preventable diseases. The earlier kids learn about diet and nutrition, the more likely they will be able to make healthy eating choices.

More people are willing to spend on organic foods by making good food choices since they know the benefits. According to the findings of the survey, organic products are mostly consumed by women and families with children. Targeting these groups through different marketing strategies has the potential to look into any specific requirements they may have.

To create a caring attitude towards organic brands or products, words such as "safe" and "healthy" should be emphasized in packaging, creating a brand image, and advertising.

Conclusion:

Due to man's insatiable need to maximize short-term profits, the use of pesticides and insecticides in agricultural

production has skyrocketed. This use of herbicides and insecticides has enhanced crop productivity and product longevity, but has also raised the prevalence of lifestyle-related disorders. Consequently, some farmers have turned to organic farming as a solution. However, this approach has met with limited success in most nations, prompting the need for a better understanding of the reasons that drive people to choose organic produce. The purpose of this study was to better understand the reasons that drive people to choose organic produce. There is still a long way to go for the organic fruit and vegetable sector, despite most participants displaying a basic familiarity with organic food products. The study found that only a small percentage of consumers in India are familiar with the core concept of organic food (without chemicals) and the India Organic emblem. Since most respondents rely on newspapers and television for news, reaching out to them in these mediums would be effective. As convenient as it would be to provide busy city dwellers grow bags and make them self-sufficient, this is not a viable option for the them. Nevertheless, with the purchasing power of rural and urban people, a large percentage of respondents (potential consumers) can be converted into regular buyers if organic jaggery are made more accessible, perhaps by increasing their availability in supermarkets. According to the study, the availability of organic produce in supermarkets will lead to a rise in their overall consumption. Additionally, consumers' perceived susceptibility of their own exposure to the adverse health effects of consuming conventional food goods over organic produce such jaggery is the one of the most important factor in driving dietary changes among consumers. Furthermore, the formation of an attitude on the part of consumers can be influenced by a variety of other elements, including health awareness, the perception of availability, a preference for quality, and an improvement in taste.

The study also found that consumers' intentions to buy organic produce were affected by their levels of knowledge and awareness subjective norms, willingness to pay, perceived behavioural control, certification and labelling, and the customers' willingness to use. The findings also revealed a few key distinctions between regular buyers from occasional and potential buyers. For regular buyers, the production method was the deciding factor, whereas for occasional buyers, the trust and satisfaction they felt after each purchase was most important. Potential buyers want to know that organic jaggery are readily available to them. Thus, the study's findings recommend that organic jaggery stakeholders take these variables into account when advocating for organic products and positively channel consumers' attitudes toward buying organic. Also, expanding the market for organic produce by gaining the public's confidence and adopt a healthier diet and lifestyle.

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